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RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>SpaceFibre on AMD-Versal: RAdiation Hardness Testing (SARAH)</i>
Project TA identifier	<i>TA10-331</i>
General application	<i>Space</i>
Type of test	<i>SEE</i>
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Date(s) of the experiment	<i>25th – 27th September 2024</i>
Facility	<i>GANIL</i>
Amount of access granted	<i>16h (2x 8h)</i>

Objectives of the experiments

The SARAH project (SpaceFibre on AMD-Versal: Radiation Hardness Testing) aimed to characterise the behaviour the space-grade AMD-Versal FPGA (XQRVC1902) transceivers and the resilience added by using SpaceFibre links, when operating under heavy-ion radiation. AMD-Versal is a cutting-edge space-grade FPGA integrating programmable logic, AI engines, DSPs, and high-speed transceivers, making it highly suitable for demanding space applications.

Reasons for Choosing the Beam:

- Heavy-ion radiation is used to simulate the space environment, particularly the effects of Single Event Upsets (SEUs) and Single Event Functional Interrupts (SEFIs) on the Versal FPGA.
- The LET (Linear Energy Transfer) range of 1-40 MeV·cm²/mg is representative of GEO and deep-space conditions.

The commercial VCK190 Evaluation Board (fitted with a grinded space-grade FPGA) served as the test vehicle thanks to the board being readily available, and also because the FPGA mounted in the board was fully representative of the space-grade part for the purpose of heavy-ion testing.

The VCK190 board is an excellent platform as it provides of access to many Versal transceivers:

- 24 transceiver lanes via FMC+ connectors (loopback enabled).
- Additional 6 lanes via SFP+ and QSFP+ connectors.

Scientific and Technical Objectives:

1. Characterise transceiver performance under radiation to evaluate error rates and resilience.

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2. Assess SpaceFibre’s autonomous retry mechanism and its impact on radiation tolerance.
3. Develop and validate additional reliability-enhancing techniques, especially for recovering transceiver configuration and registers after SEUs/SEFIs.

By improving radiation tolerance, this experiment should directly benefit future space-based data-handling and processing systems, impacting numerous European and US space missions.

Experiment test report

The VCK190 Evaluation Kit was selected as a test vehicle for the radiation campaign. This board features a VC1902 Versal part, which is the commercial equivalent of the space-grade XQRVC1902. For the purposes of this radiation campaign, both parts are considered equivalent.

Fig. 1 outlines the architecture of the tested design. The left square (DUT) represents the part of the design implemented inside the Versal FPGA and subject to radiation. The right square corresponds to an external—not irradiated—STAR-Ultra PCIe unit that interfaced with two SpFi links in the Versal (I1 and I2). The STAR-Ultra PCIe provides two independent 4-lane SpFi links via QSFP+ interfaces, with each lane currently supporting rates up to 7.8 Gbit/s. These interfaces can be used to transfer data at high speed to/from a host PC (over PCIe Gen3). In this case, I1 implemented a quad-lane SpFi link (25 Gbit/s) and I2 a dual-lane SpFi link (12.5 Gbit/s). I3 and I4 were links connected to themselves via an FMC+ loopback card, due to limitations on the external equipment available. Specifically, I3 consisted of a quad-lane SpFi link (running at 25 Gbit/s) whereas I4 implemented an experimental quad-lane SpFi link running at 100 Gbit/s (25 Gbit/s per channel).

Fig. 1. Radiation test architecture.

Internal data checkers and generators were implemented for each link, and an additional Test Monitor block was in charge of controlling the status of each of the links.

The tests were carried out in the autumn of 2024 at GANIL (France). The effective LET used covered a range from 28 to 43 MeV·cm²/mg. Lower LETs were unfortunately not tested as only Xenon ions were available during the two 8-hour test windows. Therefore, the results presented can be considered a worst case scenario heavy-ion radiation sensitivity measurement. An additional campaign is planned to test LETs < 25 MeV·cm²/mg, which would provide the onset threshold and intermediate cross-section values necessary for estimating the Weibull curves required to calculate the error rates for a given orbit.

Fig. 3 shows the aggregated cross-section for the four channels composing a transceiver Quad. This value accounts for various error cases affecting transceiver components such as the TXPLL and the data path, and indicates the resulting cross-section that would be experienced by a quad-lane link using such Quad. The blue line corresponds to the cross-section measured on Quads connected to external equipment, whereas the orange line corresponds to the same measurement on transceivers connected via a physical loopback. The cross-section is an order of magnitude greater when connected to external equipment than when using a loopback, demonstrating the importance of testing designs using a representative setup. Green corresponds to SEFI events that required board reprogramming to recover (TBC).

Fig. 3. Transceiver Quad cross-section. Blue: entire Quad. Orange: entire Quad connected in physical loopback. Green: Quad SEFI (TBC).

Fig. 4 provides the cross-section for different elements composing a transceiver Quad. In blue, the Quad PLLs; in orange, the channel data path; in green, the Quad shared logic. Either a Quad PLL or a channel data path event triggers a SpFi retry event, with recovery occurring in less than 4 μs. This represents ~99% of the total number of events. An event affecting the Quad shared logic, on the other hand, requires a full transceiver reset, lasting ~1.5 ms. This represents ~1% of the total number of events. Note that SpFi automatically recovers all these events, but they may impact operation when alternative protocols are used.

A protocol must be implemented in the FPGA fabric to enable data transmission through a transceiver.

However, both the fabric and its associated CRAM are vulnerable to SEUs, adding an additional challenge. Fig. 5 shows the cross-section of a quad-lane SpFi link. Radiation-induced SEUs in the FPGA fabric affect the operation of the SpFi IP, as shown by the blue line. These cross-section values are an order of magnitude lower than those of the transceiver Quad (blue line of Fig. 3). This difference is partly explained by the small footprint of the SpFi IP in the Versal, which uses only around 0.5% of the fabric resources available in an XQRVC1902, helping to reduce the impact of SEUs in the FPGA fabric. The orange line represents the cross-section for the same SpFi link when DTMR is applied. However, this value is still TBC, as only ~88% of the link logic was covered by DTMR—closely matching the observed improvement factor in the cross-section. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that if DTMR is fully applied to the SpFi link, SEUs will no longer have an impact on the FPGA fabric.

Fig. 4. Cross-section for the different elements of the transceiver Quad. Blue: Quad PLL. Orange: Channel data path. Green: Quad shared logic.

Fig. 5. Cross-section for SpaceFibre IP link fabric. Blue: nominal. Orange: DTMR applied to

most of the link.

Additionally, the radiation campaign successfully demonstrated an experimental 100 Gbit/s SpFi link operating under radiation. This was achieved using a quad-lane configuration, with each lane operating at 25 Gbit/s. The correct operation of the 100 Gbit/s link was validated under nominal operating conditions. However, thorough testing is needed, as it was observed that error recovery under radiation was not as robust as in the other SpFi links.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	
Follow-up experiment at same facility	
Follow-up experiment at another facility	X
Other	X

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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